

1 **Trop-2 targeting with monoclonal antibodies that simultaneously present HLA-V for NK cell tumor**
2 **surveillance through TACSTD2.**

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8 HLA-V is transiently up-regulated during or following cellular transformation and marks the transformed
9 cell for clearance by the natural killer cell in conjunction with the gamma delta T cell but is likely broadly
10 and rapidly silenced in humans with cancer. We describe here a strategy by which a tumor antigen,
11 TACSTD2 ("Trop-2") is targeted with a bi-functional antibody containing a Tacstd2-binding domain together
12 with an encoded HLA-V that uses Tacstd2 binding to deliver HLA-V for tumor surveillance by the natural
13 killer (NK) cell.

14 Citations

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